

Polymerizable wedge-shaped ionic liquid crystals for fabrication of ion-conducting membranes: Impact of the counterion on the phase structure and conductivity

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Abstract:

In this paper we report on the thermotropic phase transitions of a novel family of ionic liquids based on wedge-shaped mesogens of acrylated sulfonates with different counterions (Li, Na, K and Cs). Their phase behavior was studied by means of differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), polarized optical microscopy (POM) and temperature dependence small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS). 2D lamellar and 1D columnar supramolecular structures phases were observed. Ionic conductivity was measured by impedance spectroscopy at different relative humidities. The influence of the counterion in the structure of the thermotropic mesophases and on electrical conductive properties is discussed. Finally it is shown how photopolymerization can be used to arrest supramolecular structures on self-standing ion conducting membranes.

Introduction:

Self-assembly processes through non-covalent interactions of building blocks to form supramolecular structures have shown to be a promising route towards the obtention of materials with tailored properties¹⁻⁷. The intermolecular forces involved in the processes (electrostatic or hydrophobic interactions, hydrogen bonding or Van der Waals forces) can determine the supramolecular architecture formed by the aggregates. In the case of amphiphilies the main factors determining the phase sequence of lyotropic systems are the concentration of the mesogen and the hydrophobic effect⁵. Nevertheless,

when dealing with thermotropic transitions, the molecular geometry becomes dominant since it determines the interfacial curvature and geometry upon nanosegregation of the hydrophilic and lipophilic domains.⁸⁻¹⁰ The so called critical packing parameter (cpp), or shape factor, is used to predict the phase structure. This parameter accounts for the area of the polar group and the length and volume of the lipophilic tails.^{9, 11} Roughly, the relationship between molecular shape and cpp is as follows: conical<1, cylindrical=1 and wedge>1. These shapes tend to form aggregates of micellar, lamellar or columnar geometry, respectively¹²⁻¹³. The relative contributions of the head group and alkyl side-chains in the self-assembling process of multi-armed amphiphilic molecules (ccp>1) have been studied.¹⁴⁻¹⁵ Although the grafting symmetry, length or conformation of the hydrocarbon chains plays a central role in the molecular geometry, the shape parameter depends also on other variables. In solvent mediated transitions, the parameter changes according to the degree of hydration of the polar head. In the absence of solvent, temperature or pressure affects the phase behavior. Besides that, it has been shown that the area of the polar head can be fine tuned by changing counterion size¹⁶ and strong effect of counterion was observed, for instance, in the phase behavior of alkali metals alkanoates.¹⁷

We have developed a series of wedge-shaped sulfonates molecules with a systematic structural variation. These amphiphilic molecules carry a large hydrophobic rim and a hydrophilic sulfonate group at the tip of the wedge. Four different alkali (Li, Na, K and Cs) cations were used as counterions. Due to the low melting temperature of these salts and the conducting properties observed they can be considered as forming part of the family of ionic liquid crystals.¹⁷⁻¹⁸ Mesophase-forming ionic liquids are of great interest due to the possibility of create 1D, 2D or 3D ordered structures with anisotropic properties.¹⁹⁻²¹ It has been widely shown that wedge-shaped molecules bearing polar groups at the tip of the hydrophobic wedge tend to form cylindrical superstructures with the polar groups arranged along the cylinder axis forming potential ionic channels.²²⁻²⁴ The introduction of terminal acrylic polymerizable groups in the aliphatic chains allows a later covalent incorporation of the channels in a polymer matrix by simple photopolymerization processes. This approach has shown to be of paramount interest for practical applications²⁵⁻²⁶.

In previous work we have shown how the use solvent mediated lyotropic transitions can be used to tune the channel structure of the Na derivative.²⁶ In this paper we focus on the effect of the counterion in the thermotropic phase behavior of the different mesophases as well as on their ion conducting properties.

Experimental:

Materials.

Pyrogallol (puriss. 99%, Riedel-de Haen), 11-bromo-1-undecanol (98%, Aldrich), potassium carbonate (99%, Merck), sulfuric acid (95-97%, GR for analysis, Merck), acryloyl chloride (97%, Fluka), triethylamine (p.a. grade, Merck), tetrahydrofuran (anhydrous >99.9%, Sigma-Aldrich), dimethylformamide (Absolute, Analytical, Puriss, >99.5%, Sigma-Aldrich), lithium / sodium / potassium hydroxide (for analysis, Merck), cesium hydroxide (99%, 50wt% solution in water, Sigma-Aldrich), 2,2-dimethoxy-2-phenylacetophenone (99%, Aldrich) were used as received. Synthesis.

The synthesis of acrylated wedge-shaped sulfonate molecules, lithium / sodium / potassium / cesium 2,3,4-tris(11'- acryloylundecyl-1'-oxy)benzenesulfonate, was carried out according to literature procedures^{22, 26}. It is schematically depicted in Chart

1. Pyrogallol was reacted with 11-bromo-1-undecanol in anhydrous dimethylformamide in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate to yield 1,2,3-tris(11'-hydroxyundecyl-1'-oxy)benzene (1), which was subsequently reacted with acryl chloride to yield 1,2,3-tris(11'-acryloylundecyl-1'-oxy)benzene (2). The sulfonation of 2 was performed under mild condition by adding concentrated sulfuric acid (98%) to the chloroform solution of 2 at room temperature. The acid was then neutralized by an aqueous solution of corresponding metal hydroxide to yield different sulfonates (Li, Na, K and Cs). These compounds were later on purified by columnar chromatography. Under ambient conditions, Li and Cs sulfonates are yellow pale viscous liquids while Na and K derivatives are brownish solid waxy materials.

Chart 1. Scheme of the synthesis of lithium/sodium/potassium/cesium 2,3,4-tris(11'-acryloylundecyl-1'-oxy)benzenesulfonate. M stands for the different counterions.

Techniques.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements were performed using a Netzsch DSC 204 unit. Samples (typical weight, 8 mg) were enclosed in standard Netzsch 25 μL aluminum crucibles. The measurement steps were (1) heating from 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, (2) isothermal process at 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 minutes, (3) cooling from 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to -100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, (4) isothermal process at -100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 minutes, (5) heating from -100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$.

Polarizing Optical microscopy (POM): Polarizing optical micrographs were obtained by using a LEITZ Laborlux 12 POL S with crossed polarizers equipped with a digital camera DCM 310.

Temperature dependence small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) measurements in transmission geometry using synchrotron radiation were performed at the BM26 beamline of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble (France). The wavelength used was of $\lambda = 1.03 \text{ \AA}$ (12KeV). X-ray patterns were recorded by a two-dimensional CCD cameras (FReLoN Kodak CCD and Pilatus 1M). The norm of the reciprocal space s-vector was calibrated using an AgBehenate standard. X-ray analysis, including background subtraction and radial integrations of the 2D patterns, was accomplished using home-build routines within the IgorPro software package.²⁷

FTIR analysis was performed by using a Bruker spectrometer IFS66/S. Samples were measured before and after photopolymerization on liquid crystalline and solid states, respectively. A broad scan was performed each time from 400 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1} with a step of 2 cm^{-1} .

UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-630 spectrophotometer from 200 nm to 600 nm and calibrated with the measurements of the corresponding clean glass sheets. The band width was 1.5 nm with scan speed 1000 nm/min.

Through-plane ion conductivity was measured at 25 °C by impedance spectroscopy using an Electrochemical Work-station IM6 (Zahner-Elektrik GmbH&Co. KG, Germany). The humidity level was monitored using a digital humidity sensor (Sensirion SHT75). The spectra were recorded with amplitude of 1V in the frequency range from 100 to 108 Hz. The conductivity values were obtained by fitting the impedance spectra using a model containing a serial connection of a parallel and a serial RC-circuit.

Results and discussion:

Thermotropic phase transitions:

Acrylic salts (A-salts) were initially characterized by POM. Figure 1 shows optical images using crossed polarizers obtained from films of the four different sulfonates deposited over glass covers at room temperature. While Li (A-Li) and Cs (A-Cs) salts appear black, which is typical signature of isotropic phases, birefringence textures were detected in the case of Na (A-Na) and K (A-K) cations.

Figure 1. POM micrographs obtained from A-salt films at room temperature. The scale bar is common to all images.

POM has demonstrated to be a powerful tool in the study of the symmetry and molecular orientation of the liquid crystalline phases²⁸, nevertheless, the textures observed in this case are insufficient to obtain a description of the macroscopic morphology of the systems. The thermotropic behavior of the acrylic sulfonates was studied by means of differential scanning calorimetry. Figure 2 shows the DSC curves corresponding to the second heating, according to the temperature profile described previously. Different features are observed depending on the size of the counterion. For A-Li and A-Cs salts no thermal events are appreciable. Nevertheless, A-Na and A-K salts show both clear endothermic peaks. The enthalpy changes measured during isotropization in this case are (VALUES), which are close to those observed in

columnar mesophases.²⁹ Nevertheless, as can be seen in Fig. 2, characteristic fan-shaped texture of columnar mesophases is not observed under POM. The incomplete formation of liquid crystalline texture can be explained by the high melt viscosity and low formation rate of the mesophase.^{22, 29}

Figure 2. DSC curves obtained from different acrylic salts corresponding to the second heating.

X-ray scattering in transmission geometry at room temperature, was used to complete structural characterization, allowing to identify unambiguously the different liquid crystalline phases. The range of interest for liquid crystals was covered by choosing the appropriate sample-detector distance. A-Na and A-K self standing fibers were drawn at room temperature by using a home-made micro-extruder with an aperture size of 300 μ m. In the case of Li and Cs salts, due to their very low viscosity, glass capillaries (0.2 μ m diameter) were filled with the material.

Figure 3. X-ray 2D patterns from acrylic salts obtained at room temperature. The images show magnifications of the medium to low angle regions. Fiber direction is indicated by arrows.

Figure 3 displays the 2D x-ray patterns corresponding to the different A-salts obtained at room temperature. The insets show enlarged area corresponding to lower scattering angles. At high higher angles all patterns show an amorphous halo centered at $s \sim 4.5 \text{ \AA}$. This ring has been identified previously as due to the stacking of the aliphatic chains in the molten state.³⁰ The information obtained from scattering at low angles allows us identifying different phases. A-Li and A-Cs patterns are characterized by the existence of a unique non oriented ring, which is characteristic of isotropic phases, in agreement with the information obtained from POM. X-ray patterns show additional features in case of A-Na and A-K fibers. Three equatorial reflections (fiber direction is vertical, as indicated in the insets) are observed. The ratio of the corresponding d-spacings was found to be $1:1/\sqrt{3}:1/2$ in both cases, which allowed assigning them to 10, 11 and 20 reflections of 2D columnar hexagonal arrangement. The fact that there are not sharp peaks superimposed to the amorphous halo observed at high angles indicate that there is no order along the axis of the columns, so the structure can be identified as columnar hexagonal disordered (Col_{hd}).³¹ Both salts show close values of columnar diameters, with $a=3.91 \text{ nm}$ in the case of A-Na and $a=3.88 \text{ nm}$ in the case of A-K. Table 1 summarizes the structural parameters derived from the x-ray characterization in all cases.

Compound	Phase	hkl	d_{exp} [nm]	d_{calc} [nm]	Lattice param. a,b [nm]
A-Li	Isotropic		3.6		
	Lam	001 002	4.92 2.42	4.96 2.48	
A-Na	Col_{hd}	100	3.38	3.39	a=3.91
		110	1.96	1.96	
		200	1.70	1.69	
	Col_{r}	110	3.88	3.90	a=6.75 b=4.78
		200	3.43	3.37	
		020	2.41	2.39	
		310	2.02	2.03	
400	1.61	1.69			
A-K	Col_{hd}	100	3.36	3.36	a=3.88
		110	1.94	1.94	
		200	1.68	1.68	
	Col_{r}	110	3.84	3.91	a=6.72 b=4.71
		200	3.39	3.36	
		020	2.48	2.40	
		310	2.03	2.03	
Lam	001	4.87	4.87		
A-Cs	Isotropic		3.3		
	Lam	001	4.82	4.84	
		002	2.42	2.42	
003		1.62	1.61		

Table 1. Structural parameters derived from x-ray measurements

The number of molecules per unit cell, N_{EC} , in the 2D lattice formed the Col_{hd} mesophases was calculated according to equation the equation³²

$$\frac{N_{EC}}{h} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} N_A \frac{\rho a^2}{M} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where M denotes the molecular weight of the salts, a is the lattice parameter derived from x-ray fiber patterns and N_A is Avogadro's number. The density of the mesophases was estimated to be $\sim 1 \text{ Kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, similar to that measured for methacrylated compounds.²² The value of the height of the unit cell was derived from the position of the maxima of the amorphous halo corresponding to the stacking of the aliphatic chains, that is, 4.5\AA . Calculations indicate that the hexagonal unit cell is formed by 4 molecules, within the experimental error. This means that the wedge-shaped mesogens self assemble in tetramers, forming discotic clusters which stacks on top of each other to form supramolecular columnar structures organized in 2D hexagonal lattices, as schematically depicted in figure 4.

Figure 4. Schematic view of the supramolecular self-assembly process of the wedges to form columnar structures arranged in 2D hexagonal lattice.

Influence of temperature on the morphology and phase behavior of the Col_{hd} mesophases was evaluated. Upon heating, the Col_{hd} mesophases shrink and lattice parameters decrease. In the case of the A-Na, this decrease is above 7% at 45°C , when lattice parameter a equals 3.65nm , before isotropization point. This behavior is typical of materials with negative thermal expansions and has been observed previously in similar columnar mesophases. The decrease of column diameter has been accounted for by a softening of the aliphatic tails of the mesogene, allowing a closer packing of columns^{22, 33}. More complex is the behavior of the salts upon cooling. Figure 5 shows the evolution of scattered intensity as a function of scattering vector s during temperature variation at a cooling rate of $2.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. All mesophases undergoes a phase transition around -10°C , as can be inferred from the changes and appearance of new reflections present in x-ray diagram. This low temperature phase transition had not been detected in DSC measurements (WHY?). In the case of isotropic samples (A-Li and A-Cs) it can be observed how the unique peak present at room temperature gives rise to several reflections at low temperature. In the case of A-Na and A-K, before phase transition occurs, an increase in the value of the lattice parameter close to 5% is

observed. In this case, the decrease in temperature induces a stiffening of the hydrocarbon chains, becoming longer. As will be discussed later on, rectangular arrangement of supramolecular columns and presence of lamellar phases were identified, in some cases coexisting.

Figure 5. Scattered intensity as a function of temperature for the mesophases during cooling at 2.5 °C/min. Insets show 2D patterns corresponding to the SAXS region obtained at -30°C . The Miller indices of the different reflections are indicated (Iso=isotropic, l=lamellar, h=hexagonal and r=rectangular)

Transformation between hexagonal and columnar rectangular (Col_r) phases has been observed in several systems^{16, 31, 34-35}. Columnar rectangular phases are sometimes referred as pseudohehagonal phases. The main difference between them is the appearance of "biaxiality" in the case of the rectangular arrangement. While the cross-section of the column in hexagonal phases is circular, it becomes elliptical in rectangular ones. This can be a direct consequence of the shape of the mesogenes or due to a tilt of the discotic unit respect to the column axis. In our systems, hexagonal phases of A-Na and A-K salts can be indexed according to a 2D rectangular centered unit cell where $a=\sqrt{3}b$ as shown schematically in Figure 6 (top). The new lattice parameters in this case would be $a=6.77$, $b=3.91$ and $a=6.72$, $b=3.88\text{nm}$ for A-Na and A-K, respectively. As a consequence of symmetry break due to lattice distortion, the 10 peak of the Col_{hd} split into two new peaks indexed as the 11 and 20 of the new Col_r phase (cf. Fig. 5). The Miller indices of the remaining reflections correspond to the 02, 31 and 40 plane spacings. The absence of $h+k=2n+1$ reflections allow us to identify the symmetry of the Col_r phase as belonging to the $c2mm$ group. The peaks position remains unchanged during cooling once the new phases are formed. The lattice parameters derived from the x-ray diagrams obtained at $T=-30^\circ\text{C}$ are $a=6.75$, $b=4.78$ and $a=6.72$, $b=4.71\text{nm}$ for A-Na and A-K, respectively. This means that the supramolecular discs are tilted along b axis. Structures corresponding to the 2D lattices are schematically depicted in figure 6a-b. While A-Na shows purely columnar phase, an extra reflection at lower angles is observed for the A-K salt. The corresponding d -spacing was calculated to be 4.82nm , that is, very close to the 010 spacing of the columnar phase (cf. Fig. 6c). It can be assumed that it correspond to the first order of a lamellar phase. In fact, as can be observed in Fig. 5, A-Li and A-Cs transform from isotropic to lamellar phase at low temperature. In the case of the A-Li salt, the persistence of the broad reflection corresponding to the disordered mesophases indicates a lower rate of transformation. Nevertheless, the ratio between d -spacings corresponding to the isotropic rings appeared after phase transition was observed to be 1:2:3, confirming the presence of layered structure with layer thickness of 3.6 and 3.3 nm for A-Li and A-Cs respectively

Figure 6. Schematic view of spatial arrangement of wedge-shaped sulfonates to form hexagonal (top), rectangular (middle) and lamellar (bottom) phases.

The influence of the cation size on the thermotropic behavior of similar mesogens with terminal methacrylic substituents of the aliphatic chains and the same counterions (M-salts) was reported previously.¹⁶ In that case, all salts showed crystalline phases which melting temperature increases with the cation radius. Nevertheless, no crystalline phases are observed for the acrylic derivatives in the studied temperature range (up to -80°C) and the isotropization temperatures are much lower. This fact can be accounted for by the gain in flexibility of aliphatic tails without pendant methyl groups. The phase sequence is also different. While the M-salts show cubic LC phases for the smallest cations (Li, Na) and columnar phases for the biggest (K, Cs), the A-salts show columnar structures for the mean sized cations (Na, K) and lamellar for the extreme sizes. On the one hand, when ionic interactions are dominant among the different forces involved in the self assembly process, lamellar mesophases tend to be stabilized¹⁷. The same occurs when the size of the counterion of wedge-shaped liquid crystal is large because it provokes a decrease in the c_{pp} parameter towards cylindrical shape ($c_{pp}\sim 1$), which favors the appearance of lamellar phases.¹²⁻¹³ These factors can be accounted for the explanation of the phase behavior of the A-Li and A-Cs salts, with the most densely charged and most voluminous counterions respectively, which tend to form lamellar phases below isotropization temperature. The truncated cone shape of A-Na and A-K mesogens (*cf.* Fig. 4), on the other hand, favors the stabilization of supramolecular cylindrical structures. Anyway, as shown in the case of A-K salt, where different phases coexists, the energetic difference derived from the stored stress into the lamellar and columnar mesophases obtained at low temperature is necessarily small and can be easily affected by the size of the counterion.

Ionic Conductivity

In order to understand the inter-relation structure-properties, the ionic conductivity of the ionic liquids was measured. Films of the four A-salts (**thickness?**) were sandwiched between glass plates coated with indium tin oxide (ITO) with a contact area of $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$. Prior to measurements, the samples were annealed at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ inside sealed vials at $\text{RH}=33\%$, using over saturated solution of MgCl_2 to control the degree of humidity. The reference "dry" samples were dried and kept under vacuum prior to measurement. Water uptake was measured by weight difference on dry and wetted samples. The estimated number of water molecules per sulfonic group ($\lambda = \text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{SO}_3^-$) is shown in figure 7a. It should be expected a monotonic increase of water uptake with the ionic radius of the cations, related to the size of the coordination sphere and so to the number of H_2O molecules adsorbed in solution³⁶⁻³⁷. Nevertheless, the Na and K derivatives show the higher values under the same conditions. At this point, it is possible to assume that the formation of columnar mesophases favors the stabilization of adsorbed water into the ionic channels. This fact has a profound impact in the conducting properties of the mesophases.

Figure 7. (a) Water uptake values of the A-salts obtained at room temperature and $\text{RH}=33\%$. (b) Through plane ion conductivity of A-salts measured by impedance spectroscopy at room temperature at different RH conditions.

Figure 7b shows ion conductivity values obtained at room temperature under dry or wetted conditions ($\text{RH}=33\%$). Under dry conditions, the ionic conductivity values decrease with counterion radius, that is, with the charge density of the cations.³⁸ The conductivity increases dramatically in all cases upon water absorption. This indicates that the presence of water is a pre-requisite to reach high ion conductivity, as reported for perfluorosulfonates.³⁹⁻⁴⁰ The ionic conductivity of the different ionic liquids under wetted conditions follows a qualitatively different trend to that of the mobilities of the cations in diluted solutions.⁴¹ At $\text{RH}=33\%$ the electrical conductivity of columnar

mesophases is one order of magnitude higher compared to that of isotropic ones. As has been shown by different authors, the formation of ordered (1, 2 or 3D) ion conductive paths affects the conducting properties of ionic liquids.^{2, 20, 42} The ionic conductivity of the A-Na is slightly higher than that of the A-K. This can be explained by the different mobility of the counterions inside the ion conducting channels. According to the measured water uptake, the cation K has bigger hydrodynamic radius under similar RH conditions (K has a coordination number of 6-7 water molecules on its first coordination sphere, Na cation shows capability to accommodate only 5-6 H₂O molecules³⁶). The increase in hydrodynamic radius provokes an increase among interionic interactions and so, free movement of electrical carriers is decreased.

Membrane polymerization:

The presence of acrylic terminal groups in the aliphatic part of the mesogens allows to arrest the columnar structure using light induced photo-crosslinking. In the presence of initiator (2,2-dimethoxy-2-phenylbenzophenone, 1% w/w), exposure to UV radiation ($\lambda=250\text{nm}$) induces radical polymerization process. By using this method we were able to obtain self standing membranes of the four different salts, arresting the structure that the mesophase presents under ambient conditions ($T=25^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH}=30$). As a matter of fact, the cross-linked membranes are not soluble in CHCl_3 anymore. Figure 8a shows the x-ray diagrams obtained from polymerized membranes of the A-salts. The presence of Bragg peaks with a d-spacing ratio of $1:1/\sqrt{3}:1/2$ confirms the successful arrestment of the Col_{hd} phase in the case of A-Na and A-K salts. A-Li and A-Cs membranes show a unique wide peak, typical signature of the disordered phase. The success of the cross-linking process was confirmed independently by using FTIR and UV-Vis spectroscopies. Figure 8b shows the IR spectra corresponding to the A-Na salt before and after polymerization process. Traditionally, the polymerization process of acrylates was followed using the bands arising from the acrylate double bond, located as a doublet around 1625 and 1640 cm^{-1} , 1410 cm^{-1} and 812 cm^{-1} .⁴³⁻⁴⁵ The bands are pointed by arrows in the figure. As expected, after photopolymerization, the intensity decreases drastically, indicating successful polymerization. Figure 8c shows the UV/Vis spectra of the A-Na salt before and after crosslinking. The mesophase shows three main signals on the spectra: a peak near 218 nm , corresponding to the $E1$ band ($\pi\rightarrow\pi^*$) of the conjugation in benzene ring; a second peak at 232 nm , ascribed to the K band ($\pi\rightarrow\pi^*$) of the conjugation of $\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups and finally a peak located at 274 nm as result of the R band ($n\rightarrow\pi^*$) of the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups.^(REF) As can be observed in the graph, the peak located at 232 nm (pointed out by an arrow) vanished upon UV irradiation, indicating the disappearance of the $\text{C}=\text{C}$ groups, in agreement with the results shown previously.

Figure 8. (a) 1D x-ray curves obtained from self-standing A-salts membranes. The observed 10 and 11 reflections are indicated for columnar mesophases. (b) FTIR curves of the A-Na salt before and after polymerization. Vibrational modes related to the acrylic group are indicated. (c) UV-VIS curves of the mesophase before and after UV irradiation. (d) Through-plane ion conductivity of the A-Na salt before and after photopolymerization. The inset in (c) shows an image of the self standing membrane obtained after photo-crosslinking.

The impact of the crosslinking process on ionic conductivity was evaluated. Figure 8d compares the conductivity values measured of the A-Na salt before and after polymerization. A slight decrease in the conducting values is detected. This can be accounted for by the fact that the ordered supramolecular columnar structure is distorted upon polymerization, increasing the tortuosity of the conductive paths through the membrane. As a matter of fact, the width of the reflections corresponding to the hexagonal packing increases upon polymerization. Besides that, the second order of the 10 peak is not observed anymore. It is worth to notice that the counterion size also plays an important role during polymerization. As can be observed in Fig. 8a, the distortion of the hexagonal packing in the case of the A-K is bigger than that observed in the case of A-Na salt. A possible explanation of this fact is that the ratio between hydrophobic forces and Van der Waals interactions is bigger in the case of A-Na salt, stabilizing the ordered ionic channels due to stronger nanosegregation of the amphiphilic and lipophilic parts of the mesogene.

Conclusions:

The structure and thermotropic phase transitions of wedge-shaped ionic liquids carrying different counter ions (Li, Na, K, Cs) at the tip of the wedge was studied. At room temperature supramolecular columnar mesophases with hexagonal packing are observed for A-Na and A-K salts. At low temperature ($< -10^{\circ}\text{C}$) all salts undergoes a phase transition. The A-Li and A-Cs derivatives form lamellar mesophases while the hexagonal packing of the A-Na and A-K salts is distorted becoming rectangular. The results indicate that the counter ion size affects the critical packing parameter and the balance between forces involved in nanosegregation process and can be used for a fine tuning of the mesophase structure.

The ion conducting properties are affected by the nanostructure, being improved for ordered mesophases. The presence of water is a prerequisite to obtain ionic conductivity.

The different mesophase obtained at ambient conditions were arrested by UV photopolymerization methods thanks to presence of acrylic groups in the aliphatic chains. The ion conducting channels can be covalently linked to a solid polymer matrix. The channel structure is distorted during the process at different degrees depending on the counterion. This distortion provokes a decrease in the ionic conductivity.

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References

1. Sergeev, S.; Pisula, W.; Geerts, Y. H. *Chemical Society Reviews* **2007**, 36, (12), 1902-1929.
2. Cho, B.-K.; Jain, A.; Gruner, S. M.; Wiesner, U. *Science* **2004**, 305, (5690), 1598-1601.
3. Angelova, A.; Angelov, B.; Mutafchieva, R.; Lesieur, S.; Couvreur, P. *Accounts of Chemical Research* **2010**, 44, (2), 147-156.
4. Li, L.; Rosenthal, M.; Zhang, H.; Hernandez, J. J.; Drechsler, M.; Phan, K. H.; Rütten, S.; Zhu, X.; Ivanov, D. A.; Möller, M. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* **2012**, 51, (46), 11616-11619.
5. Kaasgaard, T.; Drummond, C. J. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **2006**, 8, (43), 4957-4975.
6. Kato, T. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* **2010**, 49, (43), 7847-7848.
7. Stupp, S. I. *Nano Letters* **2010**, 10, (12), 4783-4786.
8. Pegenau, A.; Hegmann, T.; Tschierske, C.; Diele, S. *Chemistry – A European Journal* **1999**, 5, (5), 1643-1660.
9. Hyde, S.; Andersson, S.; Larsson, K.; Blum, Z.; Landh, T.; Lidin, S.; Ninham, B. W., *The Language of Shape. The Role of Curvature in Condensed Matter: Physics, Chemistry and Biology*. Elsevier Science B.V.: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 1997.
10. Balagurusamy, V. S. K.; Ungar, G.; Percec, V.; Johansson, G. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **1997**, 119, (7), 1539-1555.
11. Hyde, S. T., Identification of lyotropic liquid crystalline mesophases. In *Handbook of Applied Surface and Colloid Chemistry*, Holmberg, K., Ed. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.: 2001.
12. Kumar, V. V. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **1991**, 88, (2), 444-448.
13. Frolov, V. A.; Shnyrova, A. V.; Zimmerberg, J. *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Biology* **2011**, 3, (11).
14. Heinrich, B.; Praefcke, K.; Guillon, D. *Journal of Materials Chemistry* **1997**, 7, (8), 1363-1372.
15. Zhu, X.; Mourran, A.; Beginn, U.; Moller, M.; Anokhin, D. V.; Ivanov, D. A. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **2010**, 12, (7), 1444-1452.
16. Beginn, U.; Yan, L.; Chvalun, S. N.; Shcherbina, M. A.; Bakirov, A.; Möller, M. *Liquid Crystals* **2008**, 35, (9), 1073-1093.
17. Binnemans, K. *Chemical Reviews* **2005**, 105, (11), 4148-4204.
18. Ohno, H.; Yoshizawa, M.; Mizumo, T., *Electrochemical Aspects of Ionic Liquids*. In *Electrochemical Aspects of Ionic Liquids*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc.: 2005.
19. Ohno, H., *Electrochemical Aspects of Ionic Liquids*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.: 2005.
20. Ichikawa, T.; Yoshio, M.; Hamasaki, A.; Mukai, T.; Ohno, H.; Kato, T. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **2007**, 129, (35), 10662-10663.
21. Yoshio, M.; Mukai, T.; Ohno, H.; Kato, T. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **2004**, 126, (4), 994-995.
22. Zhu, X.; Scherbina, M. A.; Bakirov, A. V.; Gorzolnik, B.; Chvalun, S. N.; Beginn, U.; Möller, M. *Chemistry of Materials* **2006**, 18, (19), 4667-4673.
23. Beginn, U.; Zipp, G.; Mourran, A.; Walther, P.; Möller, M. *Advanced Materials* **2000**, 12, (7), 513-516.
24. Rosen, B. M.; Wilson, C. J.; Wilson, D. A.; Peterca, M.; Imam, M. R.; Percec, V. *Chemical Reviews* **2009**, 109, (11), 6275-6540.

25. Yoshio, M.; Kagata, T.; Hoshino, K.; Mukai, T.; Ohno, H.; Kato, T. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **2006**, 128, (16), 5570-5577.
26. Zhang, H.; Li, L.; Möller, M.; Zhu, X.; Rueda, J. J. H.; Rosenthal, M.; Ivanov, D. A. *Advanced Materials* **2013**, n/a-n/a.
27. Rosenthal, M.; Portale, G.; Burghammer, M.; Bar, G.; Samulski, E. T.; Ivanov, D. A. *Macromolecules* **2012**.
28. Dierking, I., In *Textures of Liquid Crystals*, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA: 2004; pp i-xi.
29. Beginn, U. *Progress in Polymer Science* **2003**, 28, (7), 1049-1105.
30. Luzzati, V.; Husson, F. *The Journal of Cell Biology* **1962**, 12, (2), 207-219.
31. Safinya, C. R.; Liang, K. S.; Varady, W. A.; Clark, N. A.; Andersson, G. *Physical Review Letters* **1984**, 53, (12), 1172-1175.
32. Percec, V.; Johansson, G.; Heck, J.; Ungarb, G.; Battyb, S. V. *Journal of the Chemical Society, Perkin Transactions I* **1993**, 0, (13), 1411-1420.
33. Fontes, E.; Heiney, P. A.; de Jeu, W. H. *Physical Review Letters* **1988**, 61, (10), 1202-1205.
34. Gearba, R. I.; Anokhin, D. V.; Bondar, A. I.; Bras, W.; Jahr, M.; Lehmann, M.; Ivanov, D. A. *Advanced Materials* **2007**, 19, (6), 815-820.
35. Laschat, S.; Baro, A.; Steinke, N.; Giesselmann, F.; Hägele, C.; Scalia, G.; Judele, R.; Kapatsina, E.; Sauer, S.; Schreivogel, A.; Tosoni, M. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* **2007**, 46, (26), 4832-4887.
36. Mähler, J.; Persson, I. *Inorganic Chemistry* **2011**, 51, (1), 425-438.
37. Ohtaki, H.; Radnai, T. *Chemical Reviews* **1993**, 93, (3), 1157-1204.
38. Shi, Y.; Wang, Y.; Zhang, M.; Dong, X. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **2011**, 13, (32), 14590-14597.
39. Pyoungcho, C.; Nikhil H., J.; Ravindra, D. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* **2005**, 152, (3), E123-E130.
40. Zawodzinski, T. A.; Derouin, C.; Radzinski, S.; Sherman, R. J.; Smith, V. T.; Springer, T. E.; Gottesfeld, S. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* **1993**, 140, (4), 1041-1047.
41. Lee, S. H.; Rasaiah, J. C. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **1994**, 101, (8), 6964-6974.
42. Farrell, R. A.; Petkov, N.; Morris, M. A.; Holmes, J. D. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2010**, 349, (2), 449-472.
43. Bauer, F.; Flyunt, R.; Czihal, K.; Langguth, H.; Mehnert, R.; Schubert, R.; Buchmeiser, M. R. *Progress in Organic Coatings* **2007**, 60, (2), 121-126.
44. Factor, A.; Tilley, M. G.; Codella, P. J. *Applied Spectroscopy* **1991**, 45, (1), 4.
45. Lee, T. Y.; Roper, T. M.; Jonsson, E. S.; Kudyakov, I.; Viswanathan, K.; Nason, C.; Guymon, C. A.; Hoyle, C. E. *Polymer* **2003**, 44, (10), 2859-2865.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Figure S1 shows the temperature dependence of the scattered intensity as a function of scattering vector. The displacement of the reflections towards higher s values indicates a shrink of the columnar structure. The isotropization temperature observed by x-ray is in good agreement with that detected by DSC.

Figure S1. Scattered intensity as a function of temperature for the A-Na during heating at $5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. The Miller indices of the main reflections are indicated.